

Flash Flood!

Living Manual – Spring 2018

Software and 360 Videos

@SeriousGeoGames

Foreword

Thank you for downloading this 'Living Manual' for the Flash Flood! Desktop software – by Living Manual it is meant that this document will be updated regularly and dated, rather than issuing version numbers to each iteration. In here you will find instructions for downloading, installing and running Flash Flood! Desktop, and some suggestions for classes which could be run from them.

The Flash Flood! project emerged from the Flooding from Intense Rainfall (FFIR) research programme, funding by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC). NERC-FFIR is led by Professor Hannah Cloke from the University of Reading, and is a £5.2m, 5-year project featuring partners from the University of Reading, Newcastle University, University of Bristol, University of Exeter, King's College London, University of Hull, the Met Office, British Geological Survey, amongst others. The project's objective is stated as follows –

“To reduce the risks of damage and loss of life caused by surface water and flash floods through improved identification, characterisation and prediction of interacting meteorological, hydrological and hydro-morphological processes that contribute to flooding associated with high-intensity rainfall events”

The project holds a Knowledge Exchange fund, and I knew from my experience with the Dynamic Humber Project, and Humber in a Box, that games, and gaming technology, can be a very effective way of engaging people with research. The proposal for Flash Flood! was to build a simulation which would place the participant inside a virtual river valley as it rapidly flooded. Where possible, the simulation would be built or based on actual data collected from the field, and data extracted from computer models of flooding. The simulation would then be used to help communicate the aims, objectives and findings from the NERC-FFIR programme.

Myself, Dr Rob Thompson (University of Reading), and Dr Matt Perks (Newcastle University) put forward an application to this Knowledge Exchange fund for Flash Flood! under the less exciting sounding “Virtual Reality FFIR Simulation”, and we are here now because it was funded.

Humber in a Box was built by Computer Science Masters students at the University of Hull as a group project, and I was very impressed with their professionalism and sheer skill. Some of the Graduates from this programme formed their own start-up developer company, supported by the University of Hull Enterprise Centre. BetaJester, as they are known, are specialists in virtual reality and game development and perfect for Flash Flood!. They have done an excellent job producing a simulation which exceeds their original brief – a particularly nice touch are the radial menus which allow participants to switch cameras and points on the timeline in a way suitable for use with a VR headset.

There are two ways you can use Flash Flood!. The first, and easiest, is to use our 360 videos available on our YouTube channel. There we have two Flash Flood! videos, one with narration by myself, and one without any narration which is better suited for classroom exercises. The other way involves using our downloadable software and allows you to freely

explore the virtual Flash Flood! river valley – this can be done using the Desktop or VR versions of the software. To use the VR version you will require about £1500 worth of kit, namely a high-spec gaming PC and an consumer model Oculus Rift headset.

Flash Flood! is simple and easy to use. It is intended to be used in a Science Festival setting where you have around 4-5 minutes with each participant to engage and communicate what you want. It does not feature the extensive domains or extra functionality featured in the range of emerging 'virtual field trips', but that does not mean it cannot be used for the same objectives – from my short experience using Flash Flood! it lends itself well to group demonstrations and classes.

This manual will provide a growing set of teaching materials – I am an Associate Teaching Fellow of the Higher Education Academy, but I am far from a pedagogical expert so my lesson plans should be viewed as guidance only – they are not targeting any particular age group and will definitely need additional materials and context as the level of education increases. It is my hope that this manual will become populated with ideas and lesson plans from those more experienced than me – do let me know if you wish to contribute.

Finally, this manual will be structured around the goals and objectives of the Flash Flood! project, and these are listed below in order of importance as I see it –

1. To communicate the aims, objectives and findings of the NERC-FFIR programme
2. To engage people with the idea of flood risk and to inspire them to consider their own personal flood risk
3. To communicate the underappreciated role which geomorphology has to play in flooding and flood risk, and how this will evolve in the future

Finally, I would like to thank Dr David Milan, a Geomorphologist at the University of Hull. Flash Flood! has been built using much of his field data which he has generously shared with us, and the research which inspired the simulation was itself inspired by Dave's 2012 paper in Geomorphology journal (Milan, 2012). Dave also helped myself and Matt collect further data from the Thinhope Burn catchment for the NERC-FFIR programme.

I hope you enjoy using Flash Flood! as much as I have enjoyed working on it!

Dr Chris Skinner

Research Fellow in Flood Resilience

Energy and Environment Institute, University of Hull

1. Using the 360 videos

The 360 videos are the easiest and most accessible way to use Flash Flood! – they can be viewed freely via YouTube so are available to anyone with an internet connection. The videos give a similar experience to the software, but movement is fixed. As the scene is pre-rendered it affords better graphics and sound.

If you enjoy the video, please do give it a like!

There are two videos available. The first is narrated by Dr Chris Skinner explaining what is happening, and the context behind it.

<https://youtu.be/23JPhz631Mc>

The second is called the ‘Classroom Version’ as it is intended to be used for classroom exercises. It has sound, but no narration, and extended views at the beginning and end of the video so students can make observations of their surroundings.

<https://youtu.be/OWQaq85oQr4>

On a desktop PC

The 360 videos can be viewed on a Desktop PC simply by going to video on YouTube using one of the links above. By placing the mouse cursor over the video a hand will appear, and by pressing and holding the left-hand mouse button moving the cursor changes the direction on view.

On a mobile device

The best way to view the 360 videos is on a mobile device. Please note that trying to view the videos in YouTube via the phone or tablets browser will not work, and for it to work correctly the videos need to be loaded via the official YouTube App.

As with viewing via a desktop PC, the direction of view can be altered by scrolling on the screen, but the videos also utilise the motion tracking in the device, so if you move it around you will notice that the direction of view changes accordingly.

Via a Cardboard-style device

A ‘Cardboard-style device’ refers to headsets which act as cradles for a smartphone. They contain lenses and with certain videos and apps they can be used to replicate a VR-style experience. It is not as immersive as full VR, but it is pretty close. They are usually made of cardboard, and the most famous version is the Google Cardboard. These days you can easily purchase a basic model for much less than £10.

All of the SeriousGeoGames 360 videos are compatible with cardboard devices. Simply load up the video on a smartphone using the YouTube App, put the video into full screen, tap the screen and then press the cardboard goggles symbol to split the screen. Now centre the smartphone in your headset.

Step 1 – Get a cardboard headset

Step 2 – Load up the 360 video in the YouTube App and make full screen

Step 3 – Press the cardboard goggles symbol to split the screen

Step 4 – Place the smartphone into the headset, making sure the screen split is centred

Step 5 – Close the headset and view the video.

2. Using the Software

1. Getting and Installing the Flash Flood! software

The Flash Flood! software is free to use – you merely need to download it from our SourceForge page.

<https://sourceforge.net/projects/flash-flood/>

Go to the Files tab to find all the downloads (you may have downloaded this manual from the same place). It is recommended that you download FlashFloodDesktopInstall.exe

Download this file and double-click it, accepting BetaJester's license agreement (this refers to the code and Unity3D project behind the software, not the software itself).

Provided in the folder is the No Radial version of the software which has reduced functionality. If you have access to an Xbox controller (no need for the console) you will be able to access the additional functionality provided by the Radial menus - this software is available on request.

2. Starting Flash Flood!

After installation, a Flash Flood – Desktop icon will be placed on your desktop. Double click this icon and the Configuration window will appear (as below) – simply press play to start the simulation.

After a short while you will see the Made with Unity logo and then a screen with the logo of BetaJester (developers), NERC (funders) and SeriousGeoGames (us). The simulation will then begin by spawning you into the virtual Flash Flood! valley.

3. The Simulation

3.1 Pre-Flood Free-Play

The simulation begins in a 'pre-flood free-play' mode where the participant is free to move around the environment (within its bounds) and explore. The river flow will not change in this setting and the skies will remain overcast. For the best experience, use an XBox One controller (install necessary drivers first), but the environment can be explored using a combination of mouse and keyboard controls. These are –

W – walk forward

S – walk backward

A – Step left

D – Step right

Use the mouse to change direction of view and walking.

Navigation with an XBox controller uses the left-hand joystick to walk and the right-hand joystick to change view/direction. The D-pad allows access to the Radial menus in some versions, as detailed in 3.3 below.

A warning will appear on the screen when the participant is walking in the area which will be flooding during the simulation.

3.2 The Flood Simulation

The flood simulation does not start automatically and needs to be activated by the user. It is started by pressing **P** on the keyboard. At any point, the participant can be sent back to the pre-flood free-play mode by pressing **R** on the keyboard.

The flood timeline begins at 15:00 and lasts for six hours, with each being simulated in 30 seconds – therefore the flood simulation occurs over 3 minutes. Below is a summary of how the simulation changes in that time.

15:00 – “Clouds begin to gather”

The sky becomes overcast indicating the coming storm. The water levels begin to rise slowly.

16:00 – “A storm is brewing”

Rain gets heavier, water rises further.

17:00 – “The storm intensifies”

Water level gets much higher and darker.

18:00 – “Intense rainfall falls on the uplands of the river”

The convective storm peaks at this time in the uplands further upstream, although this intensity is not observed at the participant’s location further down the valley.

19:00 – “Rain water from the uplands swells the river level. A flash flood is coming!”

The flood wave upstream has formed a “wall of water” with a debris laden front which cascades down the river. Here it passes the user.

20:00 – “The flood has reached its peak”

At this point in the timeline, the participant is respawned over a new landscape reflecting the changed landscape. The shape of the valley has changed, the channels deeper, wider, straighter, and much of the vegetation and boulders have been removed, all of which is revealed as the water level decreases.

21:00 – “The flood has receded leaving a scene of devastation”

The flood simulation has finished and another free-play mode begins using the post-flood environment.

To return to the pre-flood free-play mode, press R on the keyboard.

3.3 Using the Radial Menus

You may wish to use the Radial Menu which can only be accessed using an Xbox controller. These will be disabled in the No Radials version of the software.

The images on the screen refer to D-pad on the left-hand side of the controller. By pressing and holding left, the 'Options' Menu will appear (as below). Move the right-hand joystick in the direction of your chosen Option and select by letting go of the D-pad.

The Options are –

Exit – leave the application

Reset – resets the application (as with pressing **R**)

Remove Water – removes the water graphics so the bed can be explored

Change Camera – toggles between a roving camera (default) and the drone camera (bird's eye view)

The "Time Control" menu can be accessed by pressing and holding right on the D-pad, and using the joystick to navigate to the chosen period from the timestep – select by letting go of the D-pad. Note – the simulation will not advance through the timeline in this mode.

Note – Flash Flood! is designed for use with Xbox One controllers but will work with Xbox 360 controller too – however, sometimes this causes the Radial menus to not work, or be

accessed instead by pressing and holding down on the D-pad for Options, and up for Time Control.

3.4 Exiting the Application

Should you wish to exit the application, you can do so by selecting Exit from the Options Radial menu (see 3.3), or by pressing the Windows key and closing the application from the desktop.

3. Background Information

This Section details some of the basic background information about Thinhope Burn and the 2007 flash flood from intense rainfall event. The key points are summarised in Figure Background-1, below.

Figure 3.1 - Map showing the Thinhope Burn catchment (shaded grey). The solid black line shows the boundary between the two 5 km radar pixels which cover the area. The hyetographs below the map show the observed rainfall intensities in each pixel (western pixel on left, and eastern pixel on right). The area represented in Flash Flood! is shown by the black square.

The information in Figure 3.1 highlights a key message of the Flash Flood! software - you don't have to be experiencing exceptionally heavy rainfall where you are to be at risk of flooding. The black square shows the area used to build Flash Flood!, an area which was left

devastated after the July 17th 2007 event, yet the maximum rainfall intensity in this area was around 6mm.hr⁻¹. The rain which resulted in the flooding was falling in a convective storm some 3 to 4 km away, and peaked at a rate of 42mm.hr⁻¹.

If you were walking in the valley in the area of the black box on that day you would not have witnessed the heavy rainfall. You would have likely heard the rumbles of thunder from the top of the valley and seen the water level of the stream rise, but until you heard the crash of boulders and debris from the flash flood wave you would have had very little warning of what was coming.

River/System Sensitivity

What the 2007 flash flood event at Thinhope Burn demonstrates really clearly is an old idea in Geomorphology which is regaining popularity with researchers (eg. Fryirs, 2016), known as river, or system, sensitivity. This idea, first proposed by Brunnsden and Thornes (1976) was defined as -

"sensitivity of a landscape to change is expressed as the likelihood that a given change in the controls of a system will produce a sensible, recognisable and persistent response."

Brunnsden and Thornes (1976) is referring to some kind of shock to a system which changes the fundamental character of how it operates. This could be a landslide, for example, which suddenly inputs a vast amount of material into the river, or as was the case at Thinhope Burn, it could be a rare and extreme flood.

The idea of sensitivity of landscapes was expanded by several researchers who included aspects of thresholds (Schumm, 1979), and a relaxation period where a system can recover its previous character over time (Chorley et al, 1984). From all these components, the idea can be summarised with a simple equation (Brunnsden and Thornes, 1976, and Thomas, 2001) -

$$\text{River Sensitivity} = \frac{\text{Relaxation Time (time required to recover)}}{\text{Recurrence Interval (time between significant events)}}$$

What David Milan did in his 2012 paper was to apply the idea of system sensitivity to Thinhope Burn -

- Thinhope Burn has been a stable, meandering bedrock channel for decades, with little material available to move during small floods
- The 2007 flood was a threshold event which released a lot of stabilised material for transport by eroding the bed and banks, and removing stabilising vegetation
- Since 2007, Thinhope Burn is an unstable, braided system with material available to move by small floods
- The system is recovering as material stabilises and vegetation grows back
- Eventually, Thinhope Burn will return to being a stable, meandering channel

Figure 3.2 - Screenshots from Google Earth showing the section of Thinhope Burn depicted in Flash Flood!, both before the flood (2006, top), and after the flood (2009, bottom).

Figure 3.3 – A view of the whole Thinhope Burn valley, post-flood, from the East looking West, taken from Google Earth. The area under the white square shows the location used for the Flash Flood! scene. The area under the white oval shows the most likely location of the storm which resulted in the flash flood. The hyetographs show the rainfall intensities observed during the July 17th 2007 event.

4. A Narrative-Driven Approach

Chris Skinner – University of Hull

Whilst Flash Flood! is based on an actual event – the July 17th 2007 flood of Thinhope Burn (see Milan, 2012) – it is still driven by a narrative which is not explicit in the application giving the user a degree of license to be creative. Here I explain a narrative-driven approach to guiding a participant through Flash Flood!, and is best suited for small groups of one-to-one demonstrations – in either Desktop or VR mode.

Start the participant in the pre-flood free-play mode and let them familiarise themselves with the controls.

“Imagine. It is July 17th 2007, early afternoon. It is a glorious summer’s day in the north of England. Hot and humid even, and perfect conditions for a walk. Maybe you’ve taken the dog for a walk in the afternoon sun. You come across the bottom of an upland valley, passing under a beautiful stone railway bridge alongside a pleasant and gentle stream.”

Try and converse with them here. Ask them what they notice and lead them to the features you want them to see if they are not saying them – you will get a lot of variations with different participants. Features to point out are –

- Steep valley sides
- Trees and plants close to the stream
- Large boulders
- Shallow, narrow river channel

The water in the stream can be difficult to make out in the pre-flood free-play mode, so you may need to point it out.

Press P to begin the flood simulation – remember you have 30 seconds for each ‘hour’ in the simulation. You need to drive the narrative on yet the participant might ask questions. Be flexible – it’s better to leave parts out than to speak too quickly trying to catch up. The more you do it, the better you will get at this (it might be awful the first few times, but carry on!).

15:00 – “You notice that the sky has darkened and clouds have gathered. It’s spitting, and you feel small drops of rain on your face. You remember that you checked the MetOffice weather app before you left, and it said that thunderstorms were likely for the afternoon, but didn’t say exactly where and when. You put on your rain coat and carry on. After all, it’s not raining heavily here.”

Not much changes in 16:00 so you can fill the time by explaining the above.

16:00 – “We know under what conditions convective thunderstorms form, but they are often small and don’t last a long time, and this makes them very difficult to accurately forecast. This is why your app tells you they are likely, but not exactly when and where – you should always be prepared.”

17:00 – “You can hear the distant rumbles of thunder coming from what must be a few kilometres away. The river level is swelling with water and it’s becoming dirtier as well, looking increasingly muddy.”

Again, for 18:00 break from the narrative to explain what is going on.

18:00 – “The thunderstorm you can hear is centred over the river valley in the uplands. Up there the rainfall peaks at 42 millimetres an hour, yet here where you are it peaks at just 6. The rainfall is so intense up the valley it causes some of the steep valley sides to slide into the stream, filling the river with mud, rocks and vegetation, blocking the flood waters.”

The “wall of water” begins to pass at the start of 19:00 – it passes quickly and is easily missed. You will want to alert the participant to look in the right direction for this, and you will need to be familiar with the environment to do this.

19:00 – “The backed up flood waters suddenly burst forth and cascade down the river. A wall of water surges down the river, carrying huge amounts of debris with it. It rips out trees and you can hear the sound of boulders bouncing along the river bed. The water stinks with a horrid eggy smell too.”

At the beginning of 20:00 the environment is replaced with a post-flood one and the participant is respawned – you will need to explain this to them. You have to not worry about ‘fourth wall’ issues here!

20:00 – “You’ll have noticed you respawned there. The application has replaced the data making the valley with some collected after the flood. The flood water will recede now and you can see the changes it has made to the bed.”

21:00 – “The flood is over and the river levels have returned to normal”.

The application has automatically entered the post-flood free-play mode. Converse with the participant again, ask them how the river valley has changed, referring them to what they noticed pre-flood. Answer any questions they have here.

Finally, end with a debrief.

“You just witnessed a flash flood from an intense rainfall event, caused by a small but very heavy convective thunderstorm over the uplands of the valley. These are difficult to forecast so be alert when warnings are in place. Here, the storm caused peat, mud and rocks to slide into the river, slowing the flood wave as it passed downstream, finally causing it to flow as a debris-laden flash flood. Locals described this as a wall of water and said they could hear boulders bouncing along the bed. The peat in the water gave it a pungent smell. The flood water carried a lot of debris with it, and this makes it very damaging, ripping out trees and other plants, changing the shape of the river and leaving it scarred for years afterwards.

Thank you for trying Flash Flood!, hope you enjoyed it.”

Ask them if someone else can have a go, taking the controller and headset from them. Reset the simulation by pressing R on the keyboard before starting the next demonstration.

From my experiences, this is a very good time to disseminate any leaflets or give aways you have, as participants are often keen to take something away with them – after all, this is the purpose of the application.

Reference Material

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